

JURY ID:

DATE:

NACHHALTIGE
DIGITALISIERUNG

InNoWest

SUSTAINABILITY DESIGNERS!

NAME OF THE GROUP	WHICH PRODUCT WAS DESIGNED?	I WOULD BUY THE PRODUCT?	WHAT SPEAKS IN FAVOR OF BUYING THE PRODUCT?	WHAT SPEAKS AGAINST BUYING THE PRODUCT?
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/> YES <input type="radio"/> NO		
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/> YES <input type="radio"/> NO		
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/> YES <input type="radio"/> NO		
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/> YES <input type="radio"/> NO		
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/> YES <input type="radio"/> NO		
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/> YES <input type="radio"/> NO		

